

Covid-19 infectiOn aNd medicineS In pregGNancy CODEBOOK - Meta-analysis 2 on case-based registries

Mark “1” for all that apply. Mark “0” for each variable that does not apply. Mark “the defined number for unknown” for each variable if it is unknown. Mark “9” for each variable if there is missing data.

✓ means that the variable is available in the dataset.

✗ means that the variable is not available in the dataset.

≈ means that the variable is available only in certain sites (for INOSS and George Washington meta-analysis).

T: may be extracted from free text responses

					Meta-analysis 2 on case-based registries				
Variable	Variable name	Type of data	Description/Values	Notes	COVI-PREG	INOSS	SET-NET (CDC)	GW MA	S-FDA
Person code	person_id	Character	Person identifier	According to each DAP	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Maternal age	mat_age	Continuous	Maternal age in years at start of pregnancy	May be calculated from estimated date of delivery / date of infection – date of birth	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
<u>Race/ethnicity</u>				Definitions for Racial and Ethnic categories according to the National Institutes of Health (NIH) . For the variables below, select the mother's race or ethnicity. Mark “1” for all that apply. Mark “0” for any race/ethnicity that does not apply. Mark “2” for each race if it is unknown. Mark “9” if the variable is missing.					
American Indian or Alaska Native	mat_race_aian	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A person having origins in any of the original peoples of North and South America (including Central America), and who maintains tribal affiliation or community attachment.	✗	✗	✓	≈	✗
Asian	mat_race_asian	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A person having origins in any of the original peoples of the Far East, Southeast Asia, or the Indian subcontinent including, for example,	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗

				Cambodia, China, India, Japan, Korea, Malaysia, Pakistan, the Philippine Islands, Thailand, and Vietnam.					
Black or African-Caribbean or African American	mat_race_baa	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A person having origins in any of the black racial groups of Africa. Terms such as "Haitian" or "Negro" can be used in addition to "Black or African American."	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Hispanic or Latino	mat_eth_hisp	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A person of Cuban, Mexican, Puerto Rican, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin, regardless of race. The term, "Spanish origin," can be used in addition to "Hispanic or Latino."	✓	✗	✓	≈	✗
Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander	mat_race_nhpi	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Hawaii, Guam, Samoa, or other Pacific Islands.	✓ with Asian	✗	✓	≈	✗
White	mat_race_white	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A person having origins in any of the original peoples of Europe, the Middle East, or North Africa.	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Other race/ethnicity	mat_eth_other	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Other than American Indian or Alaska Native, Asian, Black or African-Caribbean or African American, Hispanic or Latino, Native Hawaiian or Pacific Islander and White	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Race/ethnicity according to each DAP	mat_race_def	Integer	[...] = 0 [...] = 1 Unknown = [...] Missing = 9	DAPs definition if the previous variables were not harmonized with the variable in your site(s). To keep as many details as possible, we decided to include the ethnicity variable according to the DAPs definitions.	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Country of residence/delivery	mat_country	Integer	See extensive list below the tables. Unknown = 000 Missing = 999	Provide the mother's country of primary residence at time of delivery. Country codes are numbered as in the COVI-PREG Codebook.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Educational level	mat_edu	Integer	Primary school or less = 0 Secondary school = 1		✓	✗	✓	✗	✗

			University or college or equivalent = 2 Unknown = 3 Missing = 9						
Maternal height	mat_height	Continuous	Maternal height in meters Unknown = 0 Missing = 9		✓ cm	✓ cm	✓	≈ m	✗
Maternal weight	mat_weight	Continuous	Maternal weight in kg Unknown = 0 Missing = 9	Pre-pregnancy or earliest recorded weight in pregnancy	✓ kg	✓ kg	✓	≈ kg	✓ kg
Maternal BMI	mat_bmi	Continuous	Maternal BMI in kg/m ² Unknown = 0 Missing = 9	May be calculated by: (weight before pregnancy or earliest recorded weight in pregnancy) * (height) ²	✓	✓ calc	✓ calc	≈ calc	✓
Date first positive test	cov_test	Character	yyyymmdd Unknown = 0 Missing = 9		✓ Until Dec 2021 (delivery date)	✓ Until Dec 2020 (delivery date)	✓ Until Dec 2020 + some 2021 (infection date)	≈ Until Dec 2020 + some 2021 (infection date)	✓ Until Oct 2021 (delivery date)
Type of test	cov_type_test	Integer	RT-PCR = 0 Antigen = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓ PCR only	≈	✗
Trimester at the time of COVID-19 diagnosis	cov_trim	Integer	1 st trimester = 0 2 nd trimester = 1 3 rd trimester = 2 Unknown = 3 Missing = 9	1 st ≤13 weeks 2 nd 14-27 weeks 3 rd ≥ 28 weeks	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Date onset of illness	cov_doi	Character	yyyymmdd Unknown = 0 Missing = 9	First day of symptoms related to the COVID-19 infection	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Gravidity	gravid	Continuous		The number of times that a woman has been pregnant	✓	≈	✓	✓	✓
Parity	parit	Continuous		The number of times that a woman has given birth to a fetus with a gestational age ≥ 24 weeks, regardless of whether the child was born alive or was stillborn.	✓	✓ ≥ 22 weeks in all countries, except UK	✓ total number of previous live births	✓ Note: definition may vary by site	✓ ≥ 24 weeks

				Other definitions of parity close to this (gestational age ≥ 22 or only live birth) are accepted.					
Previous stillbirth	prev_stillbirth	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	History of stillbirth (see stillbirth for definition of stillbirth)	✓	✗	✗	≈	✓
Previous caesarean section	prev_cs	Integer	No history of C/S = 0 History of 1 C/S = 1 History of 2 C/S = 2 History of 3 C/S = 3 History of ≥ 4 C/S = 4 Unknown = 5 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✗	≈	✗
Pre-existing medical problems with evidence of increased COVID-19 severity				For the variables below, select all pre-existing medical problems. Mark “1” for all that apply. Mark “0” for any medical problem that does not apply. Mark “2” for each medical problem if it is unknown. Mark “9” if the variable is missing.					
Chronic respiratory disease	mv_ppcon_resp	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes: asthma, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, emphysema	✓	≈ Only asthma	✓	≈	✓
Chronic renal disease	mv_ppcon_renal	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓	≈	✓
Cancer	mv_ppcon_cancer	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
Cardiovascular disease	mv_ppcon_cvd	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes: heart failure, coronary artery disease, cardiac myopathies	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Diabetes mellitus	mv_ppcon_diabetes	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Mark “yes” if the mother was diagnosed with either Type 1 or Type 2 diabetes prior to this pregnancy. This does not include gestational diabetes diagnosed during the pregnancy.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Hypertension	mv_ppcon_htn	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1	Mark “yes” if the mother was diagnosed with hypertension prior to	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

			Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	this pregnancy. This does not include pregnancy induced hypertension diagnosed during the pregnancy.	<i>Included in cardiac disease</i>				
Immuno-suppressive	mv_ppcon_imm	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes: HIV, Immunosuppression	✓	✗	✓	✓ HIV	✗
Auto-immune disorders	mv_ppcon_autoimm	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✗	✗	✓	≈	✗
Mental disorders	mv_ppcon_psyche	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes: depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, psychiatric or psychological condition	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
Neurological	mv_ppcon_neuro	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	✗	✗
Rheumatic diseases	mv_ppcon_rheum	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Sickle cell diseases and thalassemia	mv_ppcon_rbc	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✗	✗	✗	≈	✗
Smoking / tobacco use	mv_ppcon_tobacco	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Mark “yes” if the mother used any form of tobacco during this pregnancy. This includes smoking cigarettes or using tobacco in any form, such as cigars, cigarillos, smokeless tobacco, e-cigarettes, and/or hookah.	✓	✓	✓	✗	✓
Last menstrual period	preg_lmp	Character	yyyymmdd Unknown = 0 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	≈	✗

Estimated date of delivery	preg_edd	Character	yyymmdd Unknown = 0 Missing = 9	Estimated date of delivery by ultrasound or LMP	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Number of fetuses	nb_fetus	Integer	Singleton = 0 Twins = 1 Triplets = 2 Quadruplets or more = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9	Number of fetuses in the current pregnancy	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Multiple pregnancies details	fetus_multiple	Integer	Twin, dichorionic diamniotic = 0 Twin, monochorionic diamniotic = 1 Twin, monochorionic monoamniotic = 2 Triple, trichorionic triamniotic = 3 Triple, singleton + monochorionic diamniotic = 4 Triple, singleton + monochorionic monoamniotic = 5 Unknown = 6 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Gestational diabetes	preg_gdm	Integer	No = 0 Yes, diagnosed prior to the COVID-19 diagnosis = 1 Yes, diagnosed after the COVID-19 diagnosis = 2 Yes, time of diagnosis unknown = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9	Defined as glucose intolerance diagnosed after the first trimester of pregnancy	✓	✓	✓	≈	✓
Pregnancy induced hypertension	preg_pih	Integer	No = 0 Yes, diagnosed prior to the COVID-19 diagnosis = 1 Yes, diagnosed after the COVID-19 diagnosis = 2	Defined as hypertension diagnosed during pregnancy	✗	✓	✓ <i>Includes pre-eclampsia</i>	✓	✓ <i>Includes pre-eclampsia</i>

			Yes, time of diagnosis unknown = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9						
(Pre)Eclampsia	preg_eclam	Integer	No = 0 Yes, diagnosed prior to the COVID-19 diagnosis = 1 Yes, diagnosed after the COVID-19 diagnosis = 2 Yes, time of diagnosis unknown = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9	According to ISSHP classification: the presence of de novo hypertension after 20 weeks' gestation accompanied by proteinuria and/or evidence of maternal acute kidney injury, liver dysfunction, neurological features, hemolysis or thrombocytopenia, and/or fetal growth restriction (definition according to study site is accepted).	✓	✓	✓ <i>Included in pregnancy induced hypertension</i>	✓ <i>Note: timing may not be available</i>	✓ <i>Include in pregnancy induced hypertension</i>
IUGR	preg_iugr	Integer	No = 0 Yes, diagnosed prior to the COVID-19 diagnosis = 1 Yes, diagnosed after the COVID-19 diagnosis = 2 Yes, time of diagnosis unknown = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	≈	✓	≈	✓ <i>Neonatal level?</i>
PPROM (preterm premature rupture of membranes)	preg_pprom	Integer	No = 0 Yes, diagnosed prior to the COVID-19 diagnosis = 1 Yes, diagnosed after the COVID-19 diagnosis = 2 Yes, time of diagnosis unknown = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	≈	✓ <i>Only as indication of induction of labor</i>	≈	✗
Medications				All medications related to the COVID-19 episode: <u>from positive COVID-19 test until one month after</u> . For the variables below, mark "1" for all that apply. Mark "0" for medications that does not apply. Mark "2" for each medication if it is unknown. Mark "9" if the variable is missing.					
Antibiotics all	atb	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any antibiotic used	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Penicillins with extended spectrum	atb_peni	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. amoxicillin, amoxicillin + clavulanic acid, ampicillin	✓	✗		≈	✗
Combination of penicillins, incl. beta-lactamase inhibitors	atb_penicom	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. piperacillin + tazobactam	✓	✗		≈	✗
First generation cephalosporins	atb_firstcep	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. cefalexin, cefazolin	✓	✗		≈	✗
Second generation cephalosporins	atb_secondcep	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. cefuroxime	✓	✗		≈	✗
Third generation cephalosporins	atb_thirdcep	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. cefotaxime, Ceftazidime, ceftriaxone, cefixime	✓	✗		≈	✗
Fourth generation cephalosporins	atb_fourthcep	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. cefepime	✓	✗		≈	✗
Carbapenems	atb_carba	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. meropenem	✓	✗		≈	✗
Azithromycin	atb_azithro	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. azithromycin	✓	≈		≈	✗
Other macrolides	atb_macro	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. clarithromycin, erythromycin <u>Expect azithromycin</u>	✓	✗		≈	✗
Lincosamides	atb_linco	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. clindamycin	✓	✗		≈	✗

Aminosides	atb_amino	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. gentamicin	✓	✗		≈	✗
Other antibacterial	atb_other	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	e.g. vancomycin, teicoplanin, nitrofurantoin	✓	✗		≈	✗
Antivirals all	av	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any antiviral used	✓	✓	✓	≈	✓
Remdesivir	av_rem	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	≈	✓	≈	✗
Lopinavir - Ritonavir	av_lopi	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	KALETRA	✓	≈	✓	≈	✗
Oseltamivir	av_osel	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	≈		≈	✗
Ribavirin	av_riba	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✗		≈	✗
Nirmatrelvir	av_nirma	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	PAXLOVID	✓	✗		≈	✗
Other antivirals	av_other	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Other than Remdesivir, Lopinavir – Ritonavir, Oseltamivir, Ribavirin, Nirmatrelvir	✓	✗		≈	✗
Antiprotozoals	antiprotoz	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any antiprotozoals used e.g. metronidazole	✓	✗		≈	✗

Anti-malarials	antimala	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes: hydroxychloroquine and chloroquine	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
Hydroxychloroquine	am_hydroxy	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	≈		≈	✗
Chloroquine	am_chloro	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✗	≈		≈	✗
Corticosteroids	ctc	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Corticosteroids' indication	ctc_ind	Integer	No = 0 Yes, maternal indication = 1 Yes, fetal indication = 2 Yes, indication unknown or both indications = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓ <i>Only mother</i>	≈	✓
Dexamethasone	ctc_dexa	Integer	No = 0 Yes, maternal indication = 1 Yes, fetal indication = 2 Yes, indication unknown or both indications = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	≈	✓	≈	✓
Betamethasone	ctc_beta	Integer	No = 0 Yes, maternal indication = 1 Yes, fetal indication = 2 Yes, indication unknown or both indications = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	≈	✗
Hydrocortisone	ctc_hydro	Integer	No = 0 Yes, maternal indication = 1 Yes, fetal indication = 2		✓	≈	✓	≈	✗

			Yes, indication unknown or both indications = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9						
Methylprednisolone	ctc_methyl	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	≈	✗
Prednisolone	ctc_predl	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	≈	✗
Prednisone	ctc_preds	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✗	✓	≈	✗
Other corticosteroids	ctc_other	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Other than Dexamethasone, Betamethasone, Hydrocortisone, Methylprednisolone, Prednisolone, Prednisone	✓	✗	✓	≈	✗
Immunosuppressants	immunosup	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any immunosuppressant used	✓	✓	✓	≈	✓
Anti IL6	immuno_IL6	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes : tocilizumab, sarilumab	✓	✓	✓	≈	✗
Tocilizumab	immuno_toci	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	= Anti-IL6	✓	≈	✓	≈	✗
Sarilumab	immuno_sari	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	= Anti-IL6	✓	≈	✓	≈	✗
Anti-IL1	immuno_IL1	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Includes anakira, canakinumab	✗	✗	✓	≈	✗

Anakinra	immuno_ana	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	= Anti-IL1	×	×	✓	≈	×
Canakinumab	immuno_cana	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	= Anti-IL1	×	×	✓	≈	×
Baricitinib	immuno_bari	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	= JAK inhibitor	×	×	✓	≈	×
Tofacitinib	immuno_tofa	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	= Kinase inhibitor	×	×	✓	≈	×
Interferon	ifn	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any interferons used	×	×	✓	≈	×
Immunoglobulins	ivig	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any immunoglobulin used	✓	✓	✓	≈	×
Convalescent plasma	conv_plasma	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any convalescent plasma used	×	×	✓	≈	×
Antiviral monoclonal antibodies	monoclonal_ab	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any antiviral monoclonal antibodies used	×	×	✓	≈	×
Casirivimab-imdevimab	monoclonal_casi	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	RONAPREVE	×	×	✓	≈	×
Tixagevimab-cilgavimab	monoclonal_tixa	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	EVUSHELD	×	×	✓	≈	×

Sotrovimab	monoclonal_sotro	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	XEVUDY	×	×	✓	≈	×
Bamlanivimab or bamlanivimab + etesevimab	monoclonal_bamla	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		×	×	✓	≈	×
Fluvoxamine	fluvox	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		×	×		≈	×
Thrombo-anticoagulant	heparin	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	×	≈	✓
Thrombo-anticoagulants indication	heparin_ind	Integer	Prophylaxis = 0 Therapeutic = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	×	≈	×
Inhaled salbutamol	salbutamol	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		×			≈	
Anti-COVID vaccine first cycle	covid_vac	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Mark « 1 » if the woman received a complete vaccination (2 doses) against COVID-19 prior or during the current pregnancy (>2 weeks prior to COVID-19 diagnosis)	×	×	✓ some states	≈	×
Anti-Covid Vaccine Name	covid_vac_name	Integer	Cominarty/Pfizer = 0 Moderna/Spikevax = 1 Janssen = 2 Astra Zeneca = 3 Sputnik = 4 Sinovac = 5 Other = 6 Unknown = 7 Missing = 9	Name of first dose	×	×	✓	≈	×
Anti-COVID vaccine booster	covid_booster	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1	Mark « 1 » if the woman received a booster dose against COVID-19 prior or	×	×	✓	≈	×

			Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	during the current pregnancy (>2 weeks prior to COVID-19 diagnosis)					
Anti-Covid Vaccine booster name	covid_booster_name	Integer	Cominarty/Pfizer = 0 Moderna/Spikevax = 1 Janssen = 2 Astra Zeneca = 3 Sputnik = 4 Sinovac = 5 Other = 6 Unknown = 7 Missing = 9		×	×	✓	≈	×
Hospital admission	mat_hos	Integer	No = 0 Yes, due to COVID-19 = 1 Yes, due to obstetrical reason or delivery = 2 Yes, reason unknown = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓ any reason, including COVID, does not include for delivery	✓	✓
ICU admission	mat_icu	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any cause	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Low flow oxygen therapy	low_oxygen	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Low flow oxygen provided using face masks, nasal cannula or rebreathing mask	✓	✓	×	×	✓
High flow oxygen therapy	high_oxygen	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	×	✓	×
Non-invasive ventilation	niv	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Non-Invasive ventilation is defined as the delivery of positive pressure to the lungs administered through a face mask, nasal mask or helmet.	✓	✓	×	✓	×
Invasive ventilation	intub	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Invasive mechanical ventilation is defined as the delivery of positive pressure to the lungs via an endotracheal or tracheostomy tube	✓	✓	✓	✓	×
ECMO	ecmo	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1	A life support system that circulates the blood through an oxygenating system.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

			Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	ECMO may be used to treat acute respiratory distress syndrome or irreversible heart failure.					
Maternal death	mat_death	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Maternal death during hospitalization for COVID-19 (any cause) defined as "the death of a woman while pregnant or within 42 days of termination of pregnancy, irrespective of the duration and site of the pregnancy..."	✓	✓	✓ Through birth hospitalization	✓ Defined as pregnancy related death	✓
COVID-19 severity in 5 levels				Definition according to WHO (levels are mutually exclusive)					
Level 1	mat_sev_level1	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Level 1: any recorded diagnosis	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Level 2	mat_sev_level2	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Level 2: hospitalization for COVID-19 (confirmed or suspected)	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Level 3	mat_sev_level3	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Level 3: ICU admission in those with COVID-19 related admission	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Level 4	mat_sev_level4	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Level 4: Acute respiratory distress requiring ventilation (ARDS) during hospitalization for COVID-19	✓	≈	✓	≈	✓
Level 5	mat_sev_level5	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Level 5: death during hospitalization for COVID-19 (any cause)	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Severity level	mat_sev_level	Integer	Level 1 = 1 Level 2 = 2 Level 3 = 3 Level 4 = 4 Level 5 = 5	Severity levels are mutually exclusive	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Endpoint of pregnancy	preg_outcome	Integer	Livebirth = 0 Stillbirth = 1		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

			Miscarriage/spontaneous abortion = 2 Termination of pregnancy for fetal anomaly = 3 Non-live birth not specified = 4 Unknown = 5 Missing = 9						
Livebirth	livebirth	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9						
Stillbirth	stillbirth	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Delivery of a dead fetus after 22 weeks of gestation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Miscarriage (spontaneous abortion)	miscarriage	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Pregnancy ending spontaneously before 22 weeks of gestation (i.e. up to and including 21 6/7 weeks of gestation)	✓	✗		✓	✓
TOPFA	topfa	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Termination of pregnancy for congenital malformation	✓	✗		✗	✓
Non-live birth not specified	non_live_ns	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9						
Mode of delivery	delivery_mode	Integer	Vaginal birth = 0 Elective/prepartum cesarean section = 1 Emergency/intrapartum cesarean section = 2 Cesarean section, unknown if elective or emergency = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Preterm birth	preterm_birth	Integer	Yes, spontaneous = 0 Yes, induced = 1	Birth < 37 weeks and 0 day	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

			Yes, unknown if spontaneous or induced = 2 No = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9						
Gestational age at end of pregnancy	preg_end_weeks	Continuous	range 0 to 45	Completed weeks of gestation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
	preg_end_days	Continuous	range 0 to 6	Completed days of gestation	✓	≈	✓	≈	✓
Neonatal outcome	neo_outcome	Integer	Live birth = 0 Stillbirth = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sex	neo_sex	Integer	Male = 0 Female = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9		✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
Birth weight	neo_birthweight	Continuous	Infant's weight at birth in grams		✓ grams	✓ grams	✓ grams	✓ grams	✓ gram
Small-for-gestational age (SGA)	neo_sga	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Birthweight below the 10 th percentile according to INTERGROWTH 21 curves (Villar et al. <i>Lancet</i> 2014;384:857-68)	✓ grams	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ INTERGROWTH 21	✓ calc
NICU admission	neo_nicu	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Admission of the neonate to a high intensive care ward	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Neonatal COVID-19 diagnosis	neo_covid	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Positive SARS-CoV2 PCR or antigen test in the neonate	✓	≈	✓	≈	✓
Neonatal death	neo_death	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Death of a live-born baby within the first 28 days of life, regardless of gestational age.	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Apgar score <7 at 5'	neo_low_apgar5	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A 5-minute Apgar score strictly below 7 at 5 minutes (between 0 and 6)	✓	✓	✗	≈	✓

Major congenital anomaly	neo_anomaly	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	A life-threatening structural anomaly or one likely to cause significant impairment of health or functional capacity and which needs medical or surgical treatment.	✓	✓	✓	≈	✓
Microcephaly	neo_microcephaly	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Infant's head circumference <2 SD or definition according to the local charts	✓ OFC	✗	✓ Head circumference	≈	✓
Same variables in case of second, third neonates...	neo_outcome_2 neo_sex_2 neo_birthweight_2...				✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Variables to be calculated (R-scripts will be provided):

Variable	Variable name	Type of data	Description/Values	Notes	Meta-analysis 2 on case-based registries				
					COVI-PREG	INOSS	SET-NET (CDC)	GW MA	S-FDA
Maternal age group	mat_age_group	Categorical	12-24 years = 0 25-34 years = 1 ≥ 35 years = 2 Unknown = 3 Missing = 9	To be calculated by age continuous	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc
Maternal BMI group	mat_bmi_group	Integer	<18 = 0 18 – 24 = 1 25 – 29 = 2 ≥ 30 = 3 Unknown = 4 Missing = 9	To be calculated by BMI continuous	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc
Quality of care	income_level	Integer	LMIC = 0 HIC = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	LMIC: low and middle income country HIC: high income country according to world bank classification 2020-2021 To be assessed by country of residence/delivery	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed
Month of first positive test	cov_month	Integer	February 2020 = 0	To be assessed by date of first positive test	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓	✓

			March 2020 = 1 April 2020 = 2 [.....] = 3 Unknown = 30 Missing = 31					assess ed	assese d
COVID-19 severity	cov_sev	Integer	Non-severe = 0 Severe = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Severe refers to hospitalization for COVID-19 as <u>primary diagnosis</u> or complication related to COVID-19. To be assessed by hospital admission and levels of COVID-19 severity: Non severe = no hospital admission or hospital admission due to obstetrical reason or delivery and WHO severity level 1. Severe = hospital admission due to COVID-19 disease (or admission reason unknown in SET-NET) and WHO severity level ≥ 2	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assess ed	✓ assese d
Parity group	pari_g	Integer	Nulliparous = 0 Multiparous = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	To be calculated by parity continuous	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc
Obesity	mv_ppcon_obese	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	BMI ≥ 30 kg/m ² To be calculated by BMI continuous	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc
High risk pregnancy	preg_score	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	High risk pregnancy is defined as at least one of the following variables: maternal age over 35 years, pre-existing hypertension or diabetes, chronic renal disease, congenital or chronic heart disease, pulmonary disease, auto-immune disease, HIV, obesity (BMI ≥ 30 kg/m ²), multiple pregnancy, previous cesarean section, preeclampsia (diagnosed prior to COVID-19 diagnosis), previous stillbirth Will be assessed by using above mentioned variables	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assess ed	✓ assese d

Combination of antibiotics and antivirals	ab_av	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Any combination of an antibiotic and an antiviral	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed
Any adverse maternal outcome	adverse_mat	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Yes = ICU admission or ARDS or invasive ventilation or ECMO or maternal death	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed
Any adverse pregnancy outcome	adverse_preg	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Yes = miscarriage or preeclampsia diagnosed after COVID-19 diagnosis, GDM diagnosed after COVID-19 diagnosis, TOPFA diagnosed after COVID-19 diagnosis, intrapartum/emergency CS, preterm birth, stillbirth	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed
Any adverse neonatal outcome	adverse_neo	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Yes = neonatal death or NICU admission, or low birth weight, or major congenital anomaly or microcephaly (in at least one neonate in case of twins or triplets)	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed	✓ assessed
Low birthweight	neo_lbw	Integer	No = 0 Yes = 1 Unknown = 2 Missing = 9	Body weight of the newborn at birth of less than 2,500 grams (up to and including 2,499 g).	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc	✓ calc

Country of residence code list

Afghanistan = 1	Cote d'Ivoire = 50	Israel = 98	Niger = 146	Tanzania = 195
Albania = 2	Croatia = 51	Italy = 99	Nigeria = 147	Taiwan = 196
Algeria = 3	Cuba = 52	Jamaica = 100	Norway = 148	Thailand = 197
American Samoa = 4	Cyprus = 53	Japan = 101	Oman = 149	Timor leste = 198
Andorra = 5	Czech republic = 54	Jordan = 102	Pakistan = 150	Togo = 199
Angola = 6	Denmark = 54.1	Kazakhstan = 103	Palestine = 151	Tokelau Islands = 200
Anguilla = 7	Djibouti = 55	Kenya = 104	Panama = 152	Tonga = 201
Antigua and Barbuda = 8	Dominica = 56	Kiribati = 105	Papua New Guinea = 153	Trinidad and Tobago = 202
Argentina = 9	Dominican Republic = 57	Korea = 106	Paraguay = 154	Tunisia = 203
Armenia = 10	Ecuador = 58	Kosovo = 107	Peru = 155	Turkey = 204
Aruba = 11	Egypt = 59	Kuwait = 108	Philippines = 156	Turkmenistan = 205
Australia = 12	El Salvador = 60	Kyrgystan = 108.1	Poland = 157	Turks and Caicos Islands = 206
Austria = 13	Equatorial Guinea = 61	Laos = 109	Portugal = 158	Tuvalu = 207
Azerbaijan = 14	Eritrea = 62	Latvia = 110	Puerto Rico = 159	Uganda = 208
Bahamas = 15	Estonia = 63	Lebanon = 111	Qatar = 160	Ukraine = 209
Barhain = 16	Ethiopia = 64	Lesotho = 112	Reunion = 161	United Arab Emirates = 210
Bangladesh = 17	Faeroe Isalnds = 65	Liberia = 113	Romania = 162	United Kingdom = 211
Barbados = 18	Falkland Islands = 66	Lybia = 114	Russia = 163	United States of America = 212
Belarus = 19	Federated States of Micronesia = 67	Liechtenstein = 115	Rwanda = 164	Uruguay = 213
Belgium = 20	Fiji = 68	Lithuania = 116	Saint Barthelemy = 165	US Virgin Islands = 214
Belize = 21	Finland = 69	Luxembourg = 117	Saint Helena Saint Kitts and Nevis = 166	Uzbekistan = 215
Benin = 22	France = 70	Macedonia = 118	Saint Lucia = 167	Vanuatu = 216
Bermuda = 23	French Guiana = 71	Madagascar = 119	Saint Martin = 168	Venezuela = 217
Bhutan = 24	French Polynesia = 72	Malawi = 120	Saint Pierre et Miquelon = 169	Vietnam = 218
Bolivia = 25	Gabon = 73	Malaysia = 121	Saint Vincent = 170	Walis and Futuna Islands = 219
Bosnia = 26	Gambia = 74	Maldives = 1222	Samoa = 171	Yemen = 220
Botswana = 27	Georgia = 75	Mali = 123	San Marino = 172	Zambia = 221
Bougainville = 28	Germany = 76	Malta = 124	Sao Tome and Principe = 173	Zimbabwe = 222
Brazil = 29	Ghana = 77	Martinique = 125	Saudi Arabia = 174	Other = 223
British Indian Ocean = 30	Gibraltar = 78	Mauritania = 126	Senegal = 175	Not available = 999
British Virgin Islands = 31	Greece = 79	Mauritius = 127	Serbia = 176	
Brunei = 32	Greenland = 80	Mayotte = 128	Seychelles = 177	
Bulgaria = 33	Grenada = 81	Mexico = 129	Sierra Leone = 178	
Burkina Faso = 34	Guadeloupe = 82	Moldova = 130	Singapore = 179	
Burundi = 35	Guam = 83	Monaco = 131	Slovakia = 180	
Cambodia = 36	Guatemala = 84	Mongolia = 132	Slovenia = 181	
Cameroon = 37	Guinea = 85	Montenegro = 133	Solomon Islands = 182	
Canada = 38	Guinea-Bissau = 86	Montserrat = 134	Somalia = 183	
Cape Verde Islands = 39	Guyana = 87	Morocco = 135	South Africa = 184	
Cayman Islands = 40	Haiti = 88	Mozambique = 136	South Sudan = 185	
Central African Republic = 41	Holy See (Vatican City State) = 89	Myanmar = 137	Spain = 186	
Chad = 42	Honduras = 90	Namibia = 138	Sri Lanka = 187	
Chile = 43	Hungary = 91	Nauru = 139	Sudan = 188	
China = 44	Iceland = 92	Nepal = 140	Suriname = 189	
Colombia = 45	India = 93	Netherlands = 141	Swaziland = 190	
Comoros = 46	Indonesia = 94	Netherlands Antilles = 142	Sweden = 191	
Congo = 47	Iran = 95	New Caledonia = 143	Switzerland = 192	
Cooks Islands = 48	Iraq = 96	New Zealand = 144	Syria = 193	
Costa Rica = 49	Ireland = 97	Nicaragua = 145	Tajikistan = 194	